

1st Assessment on Micro Frontends

Provide your personal information and answer the questions on the following pages about the Mercado Livre website.

What is your full name? *

In this exercise, you will need to access two documents: *

- Description of the proposed architecture to implement the website using Micro Frontends
- Slides from the lecture on best practices and examples of Micro Frontends

Access the architecture description of Mercado Livre

Access the lecture slides on best practices and examples of Micro Frontends

Architectural Inspection

Consider that you are a Junior Developer who is about to start working at Mercado Livre. You have just learned more about the system architecture and have been asked to analyze the MFE architecture:

Would you model the Mercado Livre website using Micro Frontends differently?
Would you keep the same MFEs, create new ones, or modify the existing ones?
Also consider the screens and fragments.

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Suppose the fragment that displays products of interest to the user has been updated and now includes a new required parameter: the cart items, in order to avoid showing products already in the cart. The `mfe-store` is deployed (released to production), and the cart screen starts showing an error because `mfe-purchase` was not updated to pass the new parameter.

This fragment displaying products of interest is exported by `mfe-store`.

What would you do to ensure that the change to the fragment does not cause an error on the cart screen, allowing the screen's code to be adjusted later in a gradual and safe manner?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without taking into account the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Initially, `mfe-store` was designed to support only physical products, such as electronics, clothing, and everyday items. Now, Mercado Livre wants to add a new product type: services (such as consulting, private lessons, and technical services). The code in `mfe-store` was specifically developed for physical products, with rules

involving shipping cost calculations, inventory, and handling—all aspects that do not apply to services—making development more difficult.

What would you have done during the development of physical product sales to make mfe-store more generic and facilitate the implementation of new product types?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

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Mercado Pago has identified that it is important for the site to allow users to maintain one or more favorite product lists. A user can have multiple lists and assign a name to each of them. The functionality consists of the following visual components:

A screen that displays all favorite items and the user's product lists.

A screen that displays the products belonging to a specific list:

A button to add a product to a list, which opens a modal allowing the user to choose an existing list or create a new one.

A modal to create a new list or add to an existing one.

What architectural changes are necessary to develop the components above?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding the changes proposed by you during the architectural inspection.

Suppose the cart screen displays an error that is not related to any component implemented directly on the page, indicating that it may come from one of the screen's fragments. What would you do to prevent an error in a fragment from making the entire screen unavailable?

What would you do to ensure that an error in a fragment does not cause a failure in the entire screen?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding the changes you proposed during the architectural inspection.

Assume that you are working on creating a new MFE. You need to create a new application-type component using single-spa, import all shared libraries, follow common code standards and structure, and register the new MFE in the root-config. You spent a lot of time setting up the new MFE before actually starting to develop its functionalities. How could you speed up the creation of a new MFE next time?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding the changes you proposed during the architectural inspection.

Mercado Livre is launching Meli+, the loyalty program that offers free shipping on all purchases, cashback, exclusive installment options, and free access to Disney+. The feature consists of the following visual components:

Meli+ Offer Screen: This screen displays the benefits and the available subscription plans.

Subscription Terms and Conditions Screen

Offer component with details that must be displayed on the home page.

Simple offer component that must be displayed in the user's account menu.

Componente de oferta para o header:

Modal to choose a plan.

Escolha seu plano do Meli+

×

meli+ ESSENCIAL

R\$ 9.90/mês

- + Frete grátis em milhões de produtos a partir de R\$ 79 R\$ 29
- + Até 5,6% de cashback nas suas compras no Mercado Livre
- + 0,6% de cashback com seu Cartão de Crédito Mercado Pago
- + Até 3 parcelas extras sem juros nas compras do Mercado Livre
- + Seu dinheiro rende 105% do CDI no Mercado Pago

BLACK FRIDAY

meli+ TOTAL

R\$ 27,99 **50% OFF**

R\$ 13.99/mês por 2 meses

- + Inclui todos os benefícios do Meli+ Essencial
- + Disney+ Padrão com anúncios
- + Deezer Premium por 12 meses
- + 50% OFF na Max e 30% OFF no Paramount+

Continuar **Cancelar**

Assinatura com renovação mensal e automática. Você pode cancelá-la quando quiser. Ao assinar, você aceita os [Termos e condições do Meli+](#), [Mercado Pago](#), [Ripio](#), [Meli Dólar](#) e declara que não é uma [pessoa dos EUA](#) nem está localizada nesse país.

What architectural changes are necessary for the development of the components above?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding the changes proposed by you during the architectural inspection.

Consider the following communication flow between mfe-purchase, mfe-store, and mfe-users:

1. When a purchase is successfully completed, mfe-purchase calls a function received as a parameter from mfe-store to update the user's list in which the purchased product was included (if it is in any list).

2. mfe-purchase also calls a function received as a parameter from mfe-users to update the user's points balance according to the purchase value.
3. The update of the user's total points causes mfe-users to call a function from mfe-store that informs the new total points so that new offers can be calculated for the user.

Currently, there is a difficulty in updating this flow because a single change may impact the communication among all fragments. How would you increase the independence between the MFEs while maintaining communication between them?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at Mercado Livre. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding the changes proposed by you during the architectural inspection.

Suppose that every time you make a change to mfe-security, it is necessary to run manual tests to ensure the application continues to work. Note that these tests could be implemented as unit or integration tests. How would you ensure quality without the need to run tests manually?

Finalization

To conclude, answer the question below (it will not impact your grade, so feel free to answer honestly).

Assign a score from 0 to 5 (a real number) to reflect your perception of your knowledge about Micro Frontends: